

Integration of Project based Learning Model in Music Art Learning in Higher Education

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ABSTRACT

This research was conducted to minimize student inactivity in the process of learning music arts. Project-based learning is one approach that can affect the learning process of musical arts. This study used a literature review by analyzing the results of reviews from national journals. The results showed that there was a change in student activity in class in learning music arts. This can be seen from the increase in student involvement in the music learning process and the increase in student activity increased from giving projects to students through the process of planning, implementation, observation and evaluation stages.

INTRODUCTION

The development of science and technology in the era of globalization is very rapid. This development requires everyone to have skills in knowledge to be able to compete with others. To obtain this efficiency, it is expected to start early. Education has a function in producing the next generation who are smart and competent. Education can change personal or group behavior through learning. Education is often called the educational trilogy. The trilogy of education, namely education in the family (informal education), education in schools (formal education), and education in the community (non-formal education).

Education in schools, in particular, is formal education that includes lecturers and students. Communication between lecturers and students is known as the process of transferring knowledge from lecturers to students. Higher education aims to provide behavioral change, both intellectually, morally, and socio-culturally. The learning process has a goal so that students can achieve learning targets.

An effective learning process involves communication between lecturers and students. The learning process has learning activities that can motivate and increase students' interests and talents so that they can make students think critically, find solutions to learning. Higher education is a higher education that prepares students to have skills and knowledge in facing the world of work. Higher education is a provision for students to get a better job. College graduates are able to compete with others to increase work productivity (Listia Ningsih & Andaryani, 2023);(Ciftci, 2015)

Related to the purpose of this education, goals that are adapted to the times require competent human resources that include science and technology, and art. The art course is part of a family of knowledge that is in accordance with the times. Art courses have an important function as a place to express ideas and ideas through music. A good music course is the process of receiving learning material that is easily understood, and being able to understand singing practice techniques and being able to play musical instruments. Students majoring in music arts have not followed the course well so that the learning results obtained have not reached high optimality.

Students majoring in art courses get a discussion of music material, music practice, the learning material delivered by the lecturer is the basic principles of singing techniques, types of instruments, knowing the practice in music courses and practice accompanying music through guitar instruments.

The quality of art learning has an impact on the learning strategy used by lecturers in providing learning materials and the activeness of students participating in art learning (Nuryati, 2022).

Based on the observations, it was found that the music lecturer had not provided art learning material with any strategy in art learning so that students had difficulty understanding the material given by the lecturer. Plus the inactivity of students in participating in music art learning so that other classmates are unable to understand the material given by the lecturer. In addition, art lecturers have not been able to identify students who understand music art material (Kristanto, 2017). When learning takes place, there are students who do not show seriousness in learning such as disturbing friends and not paying attention to lecturers during learning. Through the use of discussion methods that have traditionally been able to overcome the learning situation of students in participating in music art learning. This obstacle has an impact on students' incomprehension of learning music arts given by lecturers. This also has an impact on delaying the learning process that is less effective so that other strategies or models are needed to find solutions and the learning process is effective again (Widiana et al., 2021).

There are several things that need to be done by lecturers to find solutions to problems found during the learning given, (1) lecturers determine the use of learning models in providing art learning materials that are adapted to the circumstances and environment of the classroom; (2) teachers create a comfortable atmosphere so that students are able to work together and communicate during the slim learning process; (3) Lecturers make learning plans that are tailored to the learning environment and time.

The three solutions above can be overcome by using a project-based learning model in music art learning. The project-based learning model is carried out relevant to the plan and the learning design of this model is carried out with the right procedures, so that it can make it easier for students to understand learning easily. In addition, lecturers can evaluate art learning and find out the development and results of music learning in class.

There are several theories that explain teaching models that are designed with purpose and involve students in cognitive and social assignments. A number of learning models focus on the way lecturers deliver material to students, especially student feedback in completing assignments and making student positions as partners in the learning process (Huda, 2014). Thus the learning model can be defined as the model owned by lecturers in designing, giving, and creating activities in the learning process in order to achieve the desired learning outcomes

The activity-focused learning model (project based learning) is learning that uses activity projects as learning material content. This model is carried out to encourage students to explore the content of the material in a way that has meaning in each individual student and experiment collaboratively (Darmadi, 2015). Other studies say project-based learning can help students develop social skills, cause attendance lists to decrease, have fewer problems, and be disciplined.

Project based learning model is a learning model carried out activities or projects relevant to the agreed schedule and time. These activities or projects are carried out exploratorily, namely students form study groups in conducting projects and actively communicating with students and lecturers, as well as providing suggestions on the results of project work relevant to the agreed schedule. Music is the work of artists who are given to the community. The art of music comes from artists who have vocal musk forms, instrumentals, and a combination of instrumental vocals (Suherlan, 2019). Music science produces other sciences, such as knowledge of musical instruments, musical notation, music composition and others (Hardjana, 2018). In general, music can be seen as a combination of vocals and instruments in musical compositions (Jamalus, 1988). Musk art lecturers have the ability to support students to obtain good learning outcomes, but cannot minimize the impact of the importance of lecturers in delivering material in front of the class. Therefore, lecturers in the classroom have motivation in developing music playing activities (Suriani, 2021).

The description above can be said that the art of music can be said that musk art has the form of vocals, instruments, or a combination of both. Music lecturers are responsible for determining the quality of art learning in the classroom. Good student learning activities through skills in singing and playing musical instruments with comfortable conditions in learning.

METODE

The use of methods in this study is qualitative research methods (Sugiyono, 2017). Data collection is done by observation, interviews, documentation, literature studies related to music art courses. The study made observations during the learning process to collect information about the application of the project-based learning model in music art learning. Data analysis techniques use the test method for students that contain the content of the material provided by the lecturer. The project task is carried out by selecting instruments to play music in the form of guitars. Literature studies are needed to obtain theoretical references and concepts about project based learning The project based larning learning model in musk subjects is carried out for the

implementation of the project based learning model to see student activities in class. The following is a sheet of student learning activities

Variable	Subvariable	Instument Items
Student learning activities	Cognitive	5
	Affective	5
	Psychomotor	5

Furthermore, this test method is carried out to measure the ability of students in the form of knowledge, skills possessed by each individual. This test also plays a role in measuring the level of cognitive aspects with multiple-choice questions in the form of student knowledge. The project assignment is used to measure the results of project completion towards music art learning. This project assignment was carried out to measure the psychomotor aspects of students. The following is the assessment sheet for student project assignments.

Assessed aspects	Assessment Value
Relevance of concepts and practices	3
The relevance of guitar instrument playing practice	3
The relevance of the guitar instrument to the student experience	4
Total	`10

RESULT

This research was conducted to determine the process of implementing the project-based learning model on the learning outcomes of music art. The implementation of the project-based learning model was carried out as many as 16 meetings, which were divided into two stages. The first stage was carried out as many as 9 meetings then continued with project-based learning. Next, for phase II, 6 meetings were held. The content of the project based learning phase I material contains the basics of singing techniques and having faith in guitar instruments in singing. While in stage II the content material of project based learning contains the improvement of learning outcomes with the project based learning model in stage I, namely getting the content of learning material practice scales, guitar instrument practice, guitar strumming rhythm patterns that vary (Ibret et al., 2013).

The guitar practice learning material in the project-based learning model is the practice of playing the gitas instrument, which is playing simple finger techniques. Guitar learning contains variations of finger techniques that aim to

make it easier for students to understand guitar practice learning material. It can be said that students focus on receiving learning materials and students' skills in playing guitar. The application of project based learning phase I is the practice of playing C, D, and G majors. While the project applied to the project-based learning model in stage II is an increase in student competence in singing practice, playing guitar in scale C. Guitar learning material in the application of project-based learning stage II is the practice of playing chords in scales, such as C major, D Major, F Major, and G Major which have varied guitar rhythms (Sarwi, S; Baihaqi, M.A; Ellianawati, 2021).

The application of the project-based learning model in music learning has an impact on the process and learning outcomes of music art students. This can make students active and participate in music learning, that is, students are motivated in the art learning process. Students are able to understand the learning material and concentrate on doing each project to obtain good learning results. In addition, lecturers provide art learning materials to evaluate student learning development. Lecturers observe the process of applying the project-based learning model to music subjects in students well.

Learning activities

Learning requires activities in interacting in the learning process (Sardiman, 2018). The learning process transfers knowledge, attitudes, and competencies. Students involved in the learning process can improve learning models, function for planning, implementing, expanding the learning process by prioritizing student experience (Yamin, 2008). Another opinion states that knowledge is acquired through observation, experience, investigation, and work, facilities, as well as spiritual and technical (Sardiman, 2014). It can be said that every individual learns actively. The expert opinion above can be mentioned that the learning process contains activities that are not only lecturers but students. Through activities, students in learning can motivate and improve their talents, tendency to think critically and solve problems in the learning process (Agustina & Naphiah, 2021).

To develop learning process activities involves 9 aspects, namely

- 1) Develop motivation to get attention so as to make students actively involved in the learning process
- 2) Describe learning objectives to student
- 3) Provide prerequisite compatibility
- 4) Provide stimulation in terms of problems, topics, and principles studied
- 5) Loading activities
- 6) Contains activities, student participation in the learning process
- 7) Loading feedback

- 8) Contains responsibilities in the form of summative evaluations (tests) so that students' abilities can be evaluated and measure
- 9) Contain the conclusion of the material given at the end of the lesson. Warsono and Hariyanto mentioned that there are seven applications of active learning, including (Warsono & Hariyanto, 2013)
 - 1) Student participation in setting learning goals
 - 2) Focusing on affective aspects of learning
 - 3) Involving students in carrying out learning activities, especially interaction between students
 - 4) Lecture response to the expression of ideas given by students in learning
 - 5) Interrelation of class relations within the group
 - 6) Opportunities are given by students in making decisions on school activities
 - 7) The amount of time spent in solving student problems

Based on the above opinion, it is obtained that an increase in student activity in the process of learning money is achieved. In addition, opportunities for students in making decisions during the learning process.

Key learning materials on project-based learning

The project-based learning model is known as student-focused project-based learning. The project-based learning model (hereinafter abbreviated as PBL) is a learning model that provides opportunities for lecturers to manage learning in class by involving projects (Mulyadi, 2015). PBL is a model that applies projects / activities as an reward in achieving behavioral competence, knowledge, psychomorphic. Students are able to provide solutions to the application of skills, such as making research, analysis, presentation of learning products according to experience(Fathurrohman, 2017) .

PBL is an innovative learning that focuses on contextual learning through complex activities. Project-based learning is learning designed for problems that are difficult to understand, based on old activities, assignments are given to students who are knowledgeable and product-focused. Project-based learning can encourage students to be active in learning, develop student creativity and motivation. Project-based learning principles

Thomas (2000) dan Wena (2009), The project-based learning model has a number of principles (Wena, 2009)

1. The central principle focuses on learning strategies where students learn based on project-based learning
2. Questioning principles that prioritize questions that motivate students to get learning concepts

3. Constructive principles include the design process, determining decisions, finding solutions to problems, forming models.
4. The realistic principle is the real project. Lecturers are able to use reality as a source of student learning.

Benefits of the Project based learning model

The application of the project-based learning model is carried out by asking questions to students and producing project-oriented assignments. Lecturers limit the time and length of project completion, student work evaluation. After the project is completed, the lecturer responds with a summative evaluation of the project creation. The benefits of the project-based learning model are real.

- a. Increase student motivation in completing projects so that students have semangat when studying
- b. Improve problem-solving skills that have an impact on student activity in solving difficult problems
- c. Collaborative improvement is carried out through solving tasks in groups to apply communication skills.
- d. Improving management capabilities can be done by lecturers through the allocation of time and place in project completion.

Project based Learning Implementation Steps

In project-based learning, students are presented with assignments on independent topics, responsibility, confidence, and analytical thinking abilities by students. In general, Fathurrohman is explained as follows (Fathurrohman, 2017).

- 1) Determination of the project by determining the topic of discussion given by the lecturer. Students get different assignments for each student. However, students can determine the theme of the project that will be completed in learning.
- 2) The design of the task completion procedure is carried out by the student until completion.
- 3) The preparation of the project implementation schedule is designed until the end of the project collection
- 4) Completion of assignments by monitoring disen through student activities during the completion of project assignments carried out
- 5) Preparation of reports and presentation of project results
- 6) Evaluation of the process and project results is carried out in reflection of the results of student projects

DISCUSSION

The results showed that before the application of the PBL model in music learning, there was a low motivation for student learning. The analysis stage starts from planning, implementation,

a. Planning

At this stage, lecturers prepare lesson plans and syllabi for art and music. At this stage, the theory of playing guitar instruments is applied, then students present guitar playing gradually based on the theory given by the lecturer

b. Implementation

This stage is carried out by opening the learning process by students through prayer. Then the lecturer explained the application of the PBL model in playing guitar instruments. Before the presentation, students were divided into several groups to complete the presentation playing guitar instruments. In its application, in groups to understand the object of the guitar instrument then gloriously learn every key on the guitar instrument. In order to be played easily, students are required to know every key on the guitar instrument. Students practice guitar instruments in accordance with the knowledge and projects provided by the lecturers. If students have difficulty in playing guitar instruments, then students can do questions related to guitar instruments. Next, each group was given a song title as a project to complete it using guitar instruments.

C. Observation and Evaluation

Based on the planning and implementation stages above, there is an increase in student learning activities because students not only know but are directly involved in playing guitar instruments by having activities for each individual in the group. After that, a project assignment was given to each group to complete a title song with guitar instruments. This is done to measure the psychomotor aspects of students. The test used in the form of questions is then revised and is eligible to be given to students. After conducting psychomotor tests, students are required to be able to find solutions to the completion of making songs with guitar instruments. The ability to find this solution can have an impact on students' real experience in producing a project in the form of a song played through a guitar instrument so that it can contain students actively involved in carrying out learning activities in learning to play music.

The results of the discussion above are supported by several relevant studies related to this research described as follows.

Tambunan (2023) mentioned describing the application of the PBL model in ensemble learning in music art education courses. The results of the study were in the form of improving the learning process of musical arts, especially ensembles.

The PBL model can develop students' level of knowledge through ensemble music theory and pianika and recorder playing techniques. In addition, the application of the PBL model has a good impact in the cognitive aspect and has benefits on the affective aspect because students participate in the discussion of learning materials in class. Furthermore, students are motivated in following the learning process and appreciate the learning process to get learning outcomes and learning objectives (Tambunan, 2023).

Fadzillah's research (2023) explains that based on the results of the Mann Whitney test, it is stated that the significance value is greater than 0.05 so that there is an increase in student competence in earth and solar system materials through the application of PBL models with a STEM approach. Other studies say that the PBL model contributes to helping teachers cultivate students' idea responses by integrating collaborative learning, iterative learning, and authentic learning in the learning process (Fadzillah, 2023)

Desyandri and Maulani (2019) explained that through the use of PBL can improve music learning outcomes in integrated thematic learning in elementary schools through 2 cycles, from 87.28% to 90.48%. This is due to focusing on learning activities that require a long time, are interdisciplinary, student-centered, and integrate into practice and the real world. Penelitian Pitaloka (2019) mendeskripsikan model PBL berdampak terhadap hasil belajar siswa dalam aspek kognitif, afektif, dan psikomotorik yang melibatkan banyak aktifitas sehingga model PBL merupakan model alternatif bagi guru dan dijadikan acuan bagi peneliti berikutnya (Desyandri & Maulani, 2019).

Arifin's research (2019) shows that the PBL model is carried out through 2 stages, namely for fifteen meetings that have an impact on music learning outcomes. In addition, the PBL model can make it easier for students to receive music art learning through guitar instruments and improve music art learning outcomes (Arifin, 2019).

Akbar et al's research (2023) mentions several benefits of PBL, namely (1) increasing the understanding of concepts given by lecturers to students about learning materials; (2) encourage students to be actively involved in learning starting from the planning, implementation, and evaluation stages. This can motivate students' responsibility in learning interests; (3) improve students' thinking skills so that they are able to find solutions from condition analysis, decision making, and problem solving; (4) increasing collaboration with classmates as evidenced by students' willingness to interact and work together in the development of collaborative social skills; (5) relate to the real world and students' daily lives so that they acquire skills in applying them in real circumstances;

(6) improve career skills, especially the world of work by finding solutions, cooperation, communication, and creative thinking; 7) improve long-term understanding by involving students in learning evaluation; and (8) improve critical thinking skills, examine different views and make decisions logically (Akbar et al., 2023).

Based on the relevant research above, it can be said that it is proven that the PBL model is able to increase students' knowledge about music practice and theory, especially in cognitive aspects so that it is able to motivate students in the learning process so that they can achieve good learning outcomes. Next, the PBL model is able to foster students' ideas and ideas in the study of the earth and solar system. The adversary of the PBL model is not only able to improve cognitive aspects, but affective, and psychomotor agreements that involve learning activintereties so as to encourage students to think critically, the ability to interact, and cooperate with classmates.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of data analysis, it is stated that there is an increase in activities in the learning process of music through the PBL model rather than applying conventional learning models. This is evident from the motivation of students to be actively involved in learning music so as to be able to develop students' communication skills in expressing their ideas and ideas in front of the class.

FURTHER STUDY

There are three important and follow-up things related to the PBL model in learning music arts in schools

1. Learning Outcomes: learning outcomes in each subject are needed to adjust the circumstances and needs of students to the actual situation in accordance with the curriculum that involves aspects of knowledge, skills, and attitudes developed by students.
2. Selection of projects that are relevant to the curriculum and student needs. Lecturers and students correspond to the subjects of art, music and real life of students. Through this project, students are able to apply the PBL concepts learned under any circumstances.
3. Careful project planning: lecturers and students are able to make clear plans, implementation times, and expected results. Each individual is able to involve their functions and responsibilities towards the completion of a timed project
4. Implementation and evaluation: the project completion process requires feedback to evaluate the final in the form of presentations, reports reflecting the results of the project.

5. Learning reflection: students are encouraged to evaluate their experiences then discuss and synchronize between the learning learned and connected to future learning

REFERENCES

Agustina, W., & Naphiah, S. (2021). Project Based Learning with Peer Instruction Flipped Classroom Design to Improver Critical Thinking Skills and Science Literacy. *PAJAR (Pendidikan Dan Pengajaran)*, 5(2), 442–448.

Akbar, J. S., Dharmayanti, P. A., Nurhidayah, V. A., Lubis, S. I. S., Saputra, R., Sandy, W., Maulidiana, S., Setyaningrum, V., Lestari, L. P., Ningrum, W. W., Astuti, N. M., Nelly, Ilyas, F. S., Ramli, A., Kurniati, Y., & Yuliasuti, C. (2023). *Model dan Metode Pembelajaran Inovatif (Teori dan Panduan Praktis)* (Efitra & Sepriano, Eds.; 1st ed., Vol. 1). PT. Sonpedia Publishing Indonesia.

Arifin, B. I. (2019). *Model Pembelajaran Project Based Learning pada Mata Pelajaran Seni Musik Kelas IX dan IX B di SMP 1 Sewon*. ISI Yogyakarta.

Ciftci, S. (2015). The Effects of Using Project-Based Learning in Social Studies Education to Students' Attitudes towards Social Studies Courses. *Procedia: Social and Behavioral Science*, 186(2015), 1019–1024.

Darmadi, H. (2015). Tugas, Peran, Kompetensi, dan Tanggung Jawab menjadi Guru Profesional. *Edukasi: Jurnal Pendidikan*, 13(2). [https://doi.org/DOI: http://dx.doi.org/10.31571/edukasi.v13i2.113](https://doi.org/DOI:http://dx.doi.org/10.31571/edukasi.v13i2.113)

Desyandri, & Maulani, P. (2019). Penerapan Model Project Based Learning untuk Meningkatkan Hasil Belajar Seni Musik Pada Pembelajaran Tematik Terpadu di Sekolah Dasar. *Jurnal Inovasi Pendidikan Dan Pembelajaran Sekolah Dasar*, 3(2), 58–67.

Fadzillah, Y. (2023). *Penerapan Model Project Based Learning dengan Pendekatan STEM untuk Meningkatkan Keterampilan Berpikir Kritis Siswa pada Materi Bumi dan Tata Surya di UPT SMPN 4 Tambang*. UIN Sultan Syarif Kasim.

Fathurrohman, P. (2017). *Pengembangan Pendidikan Karakter* (2nd ed.). Refika Aditama.v

Huda, M. (2014). *Model-Model Pengajaran dan Pembelajaran*. Pustaka Pelajar.

Ibret, U. B., Recepoglu, E., Karasu, E., & Recepoglu, S. (2013). Evaluation of the Project Studies in social studies course of secondary schools in Turkey . *Educational Research and Reviews*, 8(22), 2176–2186.

Jamalus. (1988). *Pengajaran Musik Melalui Pengalaman Musik*. Depdikbud, Dirjen Dikti, PPLTK.

Kristanto, A. (2017). Memahami Paradigma Pendidikan Seni . *ABDIEL*, 119–126.

Listia Ningsih, I., & Andaryani, E. T. (2023). Analysis of Learning Interest Indonesian. *International Journal of Educational Technology Research (IJETR)*, 1(2), 89–108. <https://doi.org/10.59890/ijetr.v1i2.199>

Mulyadi, E. (2015). Penerapan Model Project Based Learning untuk Meningkatkan Kinerja dan Prestasi Belajar Fisika Siswa SMK. *Jurnal Pendidikan Teknologi*, 22(4), 387–395.

Nuryati. (2022). *Implementasi Literasi Digital dalam Pembelajaran Matematika di SD Negeri Sumogawe 01 Kabupaten Semarang*. Universitas Muhammadiyah Surakarta.

- Sardiman. (2018). *Interaksi dan Motivasi Belajar Mengajar*. Raja Grafindo Persada.
- Sarwi, S; Baihaqi, M.A; Ellianawati, E. (2021). Implementation of Project Based Learning Based on STEM Approach to Improve Students' Problems Solving Abilities. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1-6.
- Sugiyono. (2017). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R & D*. Alfabeta.
- Suherlan, E. (2019). Pengaruh Perbandingan antara Model Pembelajaran Direct Instruction dengan Model Project Based Learning terhadap Hasil Belajar Backhand pada Siswa kelas IV SD Negeri CIPAKU Kecamatan Sukaraja. *PAJAR (Pendidikan Dan Pengajaran)*, 3(5), 1-7.
- Suriani. (2021). *Kompetensi Profesional Guru Seni Budaya (Seni Musik) Kelas X di SMK Negeri I Pekanbaru Tahun Ajaran 2019/2020*. Universitas Islam Riau.
- Tambunan, J. O. (2023). Analisis Penerapan Project Based Learning Pada Mata Kuliah Pendidikan Seni Musik Pada Mahasiswa Jurusan PGSD Semester VI Universitas Efarina. *INNOVATIVE: Journal Of Social Science Research*, 3(3), 10037-10050.
- Warsono, & Hariyanto. (2013). *Pembelajaran Aktif*. PT. Remaja Rosdakarya.
- Wena, M. (2009). *Strategi Pembelajaran Inovatif Kontemporer*. PT. Bumi Aksara .
- Widiana, W. I., Tegeh, M., & Artanayasa, W. I. (2021). The Project based Assessment Learning Model that Impacts Learning Achievement and Nationalism Attitudes. *Cakrawala Pendidikan*, 40(2), 389-401.